

Synthesis and antimicrobial evaluation of novel amide synthesized from nonbiodegradable PET waste

R. K. Soni* and Manisha Bhardwaj

Department of Chemistry, C. C. S. University, Meerut-250 005, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : rksoni_rks@yahoo.com, bhardwajmanisha12@gmail.com

Manuscript received online 22 May 2015, accepted 01 June 2015

Abstract : The antimicrobial effect of compound terephthalic dihydrazide (synthesized through aminolysis of PET waste) and its complex formed through its complexation with lanthanum nitrate, a well known antimicrobial agent, were investigated on different fungal species after their characterization through elemental analysis and various spectroscopic studies i.e. FTIR, UV-Visible, NMR etc. They were screened for *in vitro* antifungal activity against multidrug resistive *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Trichoderma lignorum*. The conidia of test fungal species were exposed to both amide and its complex at variable concentration from 0.4 mg/ml–1.0 mg/ml media at 37 °C. The results of bioactive assay showed that synthesized amide suppressed growth of fungi and displayed better antimicrobial activities against tested strains as compared to its complex. Studies were also extended to check the effect of amide on growth, morphology, reproduction and conc. of biochemical constituents of test fungi.

Keywords : Antifungal activity, PET waste, terephthalic dihydrazide, *T. lignorum*, *F. oxysporum*.

Introduction

The increasing failures of chemotherapeutics and antibiotic resistance exhibited by pathogenic microbial infectious agents have led to the screening of several new antimicrobial agents^{1–4} for their potential antimicrobial activity. The significant clinical implication of resistance has led to heightened interest in the study of antimicrobial resistance from different angles. During recent years study of amides take a new concern about its biological active behavior. Approximately 66% of all preliminary screening reactions in medicinal chemistry laboratories involve amide formation⁵. Various studies of literature proved it as good antimicrobial agent^{6–13} they are extensively used as antibacterial as well as antifungal agent^{14,15}. Terephthalic dihydrazide (TDH) an aromatic amide, synthesized from PET waste (a non biodegradable thermoplastic polymer resin) by recycling through aminolysis, has been studied for an antimicrobial agent and its complexation was done with La-N which exerts a pronounced cytotoxic effect^{16,17} to determine whether the new complex formed will help amides for enhancing its antimicrobial activity. After confirmation of amide as a good antimicrobial agent, minimum inhibitory concentration was estimated and its

effect on growth factor, spore germination, morphology, and biochemical constituents within the fungus was determined. During the course of study, fungal species *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Trichoderma lignorum* were used which are well known for Panama as well as Green Mold diseases respectively and the causing organism for various human and plants diseases. A survey of literature reveals that no work has been done on the effect of amide on various parameters which were taken in our study. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to study the effect of terephthalic dihydrazide on the growth of fungus and to reveal the reason for inhibition of fungal growth by the same.

The objective of this research was to evaluate the potential of amide synthesized from non-biodegradable commonly used plastic on multi-drug resistive standard microorganisms so that it could be used in pharmacological area with variety of applications such as in fungicides, paints, water treatment, coating on medical devices, food packaging and health care related materials. Moreover, we also investigated the synergistic effects of amide complex in association with lanthanum nitrate against same strains.

Results and discussion

Chemistry :

Amide synthesized and its complex is fairly stable which can be stored for a long period and are non hygroscopic in nature. The elemental analysis showed a close aggregate with theoretical value. Both the compound and its complex showed variation for their solubility in DMF, THF and chloroform while soluble in DMSO on slight heating. So, DMSO was chosen as solvent rather than DMF, THF and chloroform for the uniformity of experiment. Various spectra recorded viz. UV, IR, NMR have been analyzed and compared to confirm the formation of complex between newly synthesized amid from PET waste and La-N.

UV-Visible spectrum :

Figs. 1 and 2 shows the UV-Visible spectra of the product obtained by the reaction of the aminolysis of PET waste with hydrazine monohydrate and its complex with La-N. The UV spectra suggest presence of carbonyl group and aromatic ring which was further confirmed by NMR

Fig. 1. UV-Visible spectrum of TDH.

Fig. 2. UV-Visible spectrum of TDH and its complex.

spectra. The figures shows strong absorption at about 200–400 nm.

FTIR spectrum :

On the basis of analysis done according to FTIR spectra (Fig. 3 and Fig. 4) of yellow precipitate of terephthalic dihydrazide and its complex, it was found that frequencies for N-H, =C-H and C-N stretching are nearly same in both the spectra, however a decrease in wave number for C=O stretching has been observed. The shift of C=O stretching vibration frequency towards lower wave number by difference of 8 cm^{-1} for first band and difference of 5 cm^{-1} for second band indicates that the amide has formed coordinate bond with lanthanum through oxygen atom. Further analysis of spectra also shows the introduction of new band in spectrum of complex at wave

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of TDH.

Fig. 4. FTIR spectra of TDH and its complex.

number 475, absence of which from spectrum of amide confirms the occurrence of metal ligand bonding and formation of complex. The infrared spectrum of ligand was devoid of absorption characteristic in the range of 400–500 cm^{-1} while notable peaks are observed in spectrum of complex in the same region. It confirms the coordination of ligand with metal has been occurred in complex. At the same time a considerable bathochromic shifts in the peaks of carbonyl group of amide is observed in the spectra of complex which indicates a decrease in the stretching force constant of C=O bond as a consequence of the coordination of metal with ligand is through oxygen atom^{18–20}.

Proton-NMR spectrum :

Fig. 5 shows the proton-NMR spectra of aminolysed end product TDH. The three NMR peaks are observed at 4.537 (4H, s, NHNH_2), 7.864 (4H, s, Ar-H) and 9.880 (2H, s, NHNH_2). The ^1H NMR spectra of La complex of TDH showed in Fig. 6 shows signals at approximately similar δ value as that of amide. This indicates that important chemical shifts for amide have not changed by

Fig. 5. ^1H NMR spectrum of TDH.

Fig. 6. ^1H NMR spectrum of TDH and its complex.

coordination. It also suggests that coordination is through oxygen.

On the basis of above discussed elemental and spectral analysis, the proposed structure of amide and complex synthesized between amide and lanthanum nitrate is as follow :

Terephthalic dihydrazide

Terephthalic dihydrazide and La-N complex

Pharmacology :

In the present study, antimicrobial effect of terephthalic dihydrazide and its complex with La-N was also investigated through linear extinction method against two fungal strain i.e. *F. oxysporum* and *T. lignorum* in PDA media. Inhibitory action of amide and its complex have been observed by taking the conc. about 1 mg/ml of compound and observation was taken after 72–120 h of incubation.

Antimicrobial activity :

Results observed in Figs. 7 and 8 depicted that terephthalic dihydrazide itself is more efficient antifungal agent as compared to its complex. Although its complex also inhibits the fungal growth but not up to comparable extent of amide. Observations on effect of TDH and its complex with La-N at temperature 37 °C and pH 6.5 showed that both exhibit inhibition against *F. oxysporum* and *T. lignorum* in similar manner. This antifungal activity of amide synthesized is might be because of various reasons as found in the literature^{21–25}. Here, this may be because of the surface activity of amide in solvent DMSO as antimicrobial activity of a specific compound is related to its surface activity in a particular solvent system²⁶ might exhibit its antifungal action. At the same time the antimicrobial activity of the La-complex is also shown upto some extent which may be related to ionic radius of La^{3+} . It has been reported that the antimicrobial activity of a complex is influenced by its stability, the lower the sta-

Fig. 7. Effect of TDH and its complex with La-N on *F. oxysporum* : (a) terephthalic dihydrazide, (b) terephthalic dihydrazide + La-N.

Fig. 8. Effect of TDH and its complex with La-N on *T. lignorum* : (a) terephthalic dihydrazide, (b) terephthalic dihydrazide + La-N.

bility of the complex the greater the antimicrobial activity^{27,28}. This is probably because they have more free ions in the solution, which can enhance the cooperative interaction between the metal ions and the ligands.

Minimum inhibitory concentration :

Results from effect of amide on fungi were motivated to investigate the minimum inhibitory concentration of terephthalic dihydrazide. MIC is defined as the lowest concentration of antimicrobial substance which, under defined *in vitro* conditions, prevents the growth of microbes. The data in the form of photographic observation and table given below are upto only minimum concentration where total growth was inhibited. From the given observations in Fig. 9 and Table 1 for determining MIC in case of *F. oxysporum*, compound showed no effect on colour with the inhibition of fungal growth and became remarkable sensitive for growth inhibition at concentration of 140 mg/250 ml media. The growth decreased gradually with the increase in concentration and gave total inhibition at concentration of 200 mg/250 ml media. While in case of *T. lignorum* as shown in Fig. 10 and Table 2 respectively the colour of the fungal colony remain green up to 190 mg conc. and change to white during full inhibition at 200 mg conc. Size decreased consistently up to

Fig. 9. Photographic observations during determination of MIC for *F. oxysporum* against terephthalic dihydrazide.

Table 1. Growth region of *F. oxysporum* measured in the form of radii obtained through linear extinction method for determining MIC using various amide concentrations

Conc. of compd.	Blank (cm)	DMSO (cm)	TDH (cm)
100	4.7	4.4	2.5
110	4.7	4.4	2.2
120	4.7	4.4	2.0
130	4.7	4.4	1.6
140	4.7	4.4	1.4
150	4.7	4.4	1.0
160	4.7	4.4	0.8
170	4.7	4.4	0.5
180	4.7	4.4	0.4
190	4.7	4.4	0.2
200	4.7	4.4	No growth

Table 2. Growth region of *T. lignorum* measured in the form of radii obtained through linear extinction method for determining MIC using various amide concentrations

Conc. of compd.	Blank (cm)	DMSO (cm)	TDH (cm)
100	4.5	4.2	2.2
110	4.5	4.2	2.0
120	4.5	4.2	1.7
130	4.5	4.2	1.4
140	4.5	4.2	1.2
150	4.5	4.2	1.0
160	4.5	4.2	0.8
170	4.5	4.2	0.6
180	4.5	4.2	0.4
190	4.5	4.2	0.2
200	4.5	4.2	No growth

Fig. 10. Photographic observations during determination of MIC for *T. lignorum* against terephthalic dihydrazide.

160 mg conc. and decrease fastly after that So, on conclusion *T. lignorum* showed lesser and slower susceptibility against the compound up to 160 mg of concentration and at 200 mg conc. growth was totally inhibited by the terephthalic dihydrazide.

Biochemical studies :

Further the studies were proceeded to assay the effect of TDH on morphology, growth, reproduction and biochemical analysis. These studies were carried out at the

concentration of 0.76 mg/ml of media at which there is no total inhibition occur but only least growth are found which is required to analyse the effect of TDH .

Effect of terephthalic dihydrazide on morphology of test fungi :

Fungal colonies are able to exhibit different morphologies depending on the environmental conditions. This allows them to cope with and adapt to external changes. When grown in solid or semisolid media the bulk of the colony is compact and several morphological transitions have been reported to occur as the external conditions are varied. Microscopic examination of fungal species showed that germination started after 18–20 h of incubation. Presence of compound delayed the germination of conidia. The mycelia that developed in control and DMSO treated media were examined firstly after 24 h using an inverted digital microscope. The smoothness of the hyphal wall appeared to be affected in DMSO treated culture. The visual examination of treated culture shows dispersion of cell wall as treated with test amide TDH. The observations in case of *F. oxysporum* (Fig. 11) under light microscopy showed that morphology of fungus has changed from clearly seen sickle shaped, thin cell wall having foot shaped basal cell microconidia and non septate ellipsoidal-cylindrical macroconidia to septate and hyaline hyphe and broken macroconidia mainly when treated with DMSO in media. While disruption of both micro and macroconidia which can clearly seen in case when fungus grown under the treatment of TDH. Both micro and macroconidia get

Fig. 11. Light microphotograph of *F. oxysporum* mycelium growing on PDA media at 40x : (a) *F. oxysporum* grown as control in nutritive blank media, (b) *F. oxysporum* grown as growth control in media having solvent DMSO and (c) *F. oxysporum* grown as test in media having terephthalic dihydrazide dissolved in DMSO.

detached to hyphae and move freely. Also loss of false head and a foot shaped basal cell and presence of chlamydospores can be clearly observed. Morphological variations are similarly observed in *T. lignorum* (Fig. 12) when grown in presence of amide. In the parental wild type strain which was grown under control conditions septate hyphae, conidiophores, phialides and conidia are observed in hyaline form. Conidiophores are branched and show

Fig. 12. Light microphotograph of *T. lignorum* mycelium growing on PDA media at 40x : (a) *T. lignorum* grown as control in nutritive blank media, (b) *T. lignorum* grown as growth control in media having solvent DMSO and (c) *T. lignorum* grown as test in media having terephthalic dihydrazide dissolved in DMSO.

pyramidal arrangements. Phialides seems solitary and branched, flask shaped, inflated at the base and is attached to the conidiophores at right angles. Conidia are one celled and round or ellipsoidal in shape while the structures get disrupted in the presence of DMSO. The changes in presence of TDH were associated with no differentiations of hyphae, conidiophores and phialides. Instead cell forms clump might be because of instability cause in enzymes responsible for stable fungal cell structure.

Effect of terephthalic dihydrazide on growth of fungus :

During submerged growth, many filamentous fungi may grow either as free mycelia or as pellets and the growth form is determined by a numbers of factors such as growth medium, size of inoculum and physical environment²⁹. Therefore, distinct cultivation conditions result in different morphological and physico-chemical characteristics of fungal hyphal elements and thereby their tendency to aggregate³⁰. Data revealed in the above studies showed that both fungi were more sensitive against terephthalic dihydrazide in compare to the growth occur in control and growth control condition. They showed decrease in linear growth rate culture (Table 6) followed by decrease in dry weight (Table 4) of mass culture. Amide showed its impact much on spores and mycelium of *T. lignorum* which shows lesser dry weight measurement. Mycelium affected with compound showed lesser growth as compared to spores so TDH might affect cell

Table 3. Comparative effect of TDH on growth region of test fungal species through linear extinction method

Fungus	Type of media		
	Control (cm)	Growth control	Compound
<i>F. oxysporum</i>	4.7	4.7	0.2
<i>T. lignorum</i>	4.2	4.0	0.2

Table 4. Comparative effect of TDH on dry weight of mycelium and spores of test fungal species

Media	<i>F. oxysporum</i> (Dry weight in mg)			<i>T. lignorum</i> (Dry weight in mg)		
	Blank	DMSO	Compd.	Blank	DMSO	Compd.
PD broth for mycelium	612	584	514	592	496	122
PD agar for spores	850	272	373	922	852	750

wall and alters its permeability³¹⁻³³ as well as cell proliferation and maturity due to its reducing spore relation.

Effect of terephthalic dihydrazide on reproduction of fungus :

Fungal reproduction is complex, reflecting the differences in lifestyles and genetic makeup within this kingdom of organisms³⁴. It is estimated that a third of all fungi reproduce by different modes of propagation, environmental conditions trigger genetically determined developmental states that lead to the creation of specialized structures for sexual and asexual reproduction. These structures aid reproduction by efficiently dispersing spores or spore containing propagules. Results obtained from the effect of TDH at 0.76 mg/ml media on spore germination of fungi under investigation, cause an interesting inhibition in growth rate in each fungal species (Table 5).

Effect of terephthalic dihydrazide on biochemical changes during fungal growth :

For conducting the study of changes in carbohydrate and nucleic acid constituents, fractionations of dried cells of test fungal strains have done through the method given by Gottlieb and Van Etten³⁵. Fraction 1 and 4 was used for assaying effect of TDH on carbohydrate and nucleic acid concentration.

Carbohydrate :

Both pathogenic fungi were treated with test compound TDH to determine its effect on their carbohydrate content (Table 6). In this study it was found that carbohydrate

contents decreased in case of *T. lignorum* when treated with test compound while increased in *F. oxysporum* on treatment. This observed alteration within the fungi whose growth was similarly inhibited by test compound on same concentration presumably due to the effect of compound in their metabolism as in abnormal translocation or in carbohydrate synthesis³⁶. The above results may also be due to the effect of compound differentially on the activity of enzyme involved in glycogenesis during growth of pathogenic fungi³⁷.

Nucleic acid :

Tables 7 and 8 shows the effect of test compound on concentration of DNA and RNA content respectively in studied pathogenic fungi. Table demonstrate that relatively effect on DNA and RNA content in both the fungi as DNA and RNA content increases in *T. lignorum* when treated with test compound TDH while more contents are present in untreated *F. oxysporum*. This might be due to the altered effect on nitrate reductase system^{38,39}.

Table 5. Comparative effect of TDH on number of spores germination in various test fungal strains

Fungus	No. of spores (10 ⁻⁴ cm ³)		
	Blank	DMSO	Compd.
<i>F. oxysporum</i>	2888 × 10 ³	112 × 10 ³	112 × 10 ³
<i>T. lignorum</i>	4880 × 10 ³	880 × 10 ³	386 × 10 ³

Table 6. Comparative effect of TDH on concentration of carbohydrate in mycelium and spores of test fungal species

Fungus	<i>F. oxysporum</i>			<i>T. lignorum</i>		
	(mg)			(mg)		
Media	Blank	DMSO	Compd.	Blank	DMSO	Compd.
PD broth for mycelium	4.55	4.70	4.69	1.3	0.90	0.68
PD agar for spores	1.50	1.70	2.19	1.22	1.19	0.91

Table 7. Comparative effect of TDH on concentration of DNA in mycelium and spores of test fungal species

Fungus	<i>F. oxysporum</i>			<i>T. lignorum</i>		
	(mg)			(mg)		
Media	Blank	DMSO	Compd.	Blank	DMSO	Compd.
PD broth for mycelium	6.03	6.66	5.10	1.76	1.6	3.81
PD agar for spores	2.43	2.22	2.08	1.20	2.69	3.40

Table 8. Comparative effect of TDH on concentration of RNA in mycelium and spores of test fungal species

Fungus	<i>F. oxysporum</i>			<i>T. lignorum</i>		
	(mg)			(mg)		
Media	Blank	DMSO	Compd.	Blank	DMSO	Compd.
PD broth for mycelium	55.5	705	276	600.6	316.2	1406.6
PD agar for spores	367.5	141	258	116.5	277.7	301.4

Material and methods :

Synthesis of terephthalic dihydrazide :

Terephthalic dihydrazide has been synthesized through complete depolymerization of PET flakes with hydrazine monohydrates as per process given by Soni *et al.*⁴⁰. The aminolysis of PET waste with hydrazine monohydrate to produce terephthalic dihydrazide is as follow :

Spectroscopic measurement :

The synthesized compound and the complex were characterized and compared through, elemental analysis for C, H and N which was performed according to micro analytical procedure and various spectroscopic studies i.e. UV-Visible, FTIR and NMR etc. The UV spectra were recorded on Systronic Double beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer (200–800 λ). The FTIR spectra was recorded on Shimadzu (4000–400 cm^{-1}) and the ^1H NMR spectra were recorded at ambient temperature on Bruker WP 250 (250 MHz) spectrometer in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$. Chemical shifts are given in ppm, downfield from TMS.

Pharmacological study :

Potato dextrose agar medium for fungal cultures was prepared and sterilized as instructed by the manufacturers (Himedia, India).

Antifungal activity :

Antifungal effect of amide and its complex with La-N were investigated for physiological parameter i.e. size, colour and density of microbial colony through cork-borer method by using PDA media for fungus.

In this study both fungal species viz. *F. oxysporum* and *T. lignorum*, were cultured in PDA media. Media was poured into 6 Petri dishes, out of which 2 used as blank, 2 with DMSO (1 blank and 1 DMSO for each fungi) and rest were used for test compound either its amide or its complex (1 mg/ml media). Replicas were also prepared simultaneously. The cylinders were incubated at 25–30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and measurements are made after 48–72 h. The diameter of the colony minus the diameter of the original inoculums disc (5–7 mm) is a measure of linear growth. An attempt has also made to find out minimum inhibitory concentration by taking variable concentration of test compound TDH from 0.4 mg/ml media – 1.0 mg/ml media dissolved in similar concentration of solvent DMSO i.e. 0.02 ml (which further can be write

as 100 mg/250 ml media – 250 mg/250 ml media).

Growth region and dry weight :

The growth region for linear extinction method was measured by measuring growth of fungi linearly (Table 6) from centre of inoculums cylinder to largest periphery of fungal growth region. Dry weight estimations were also done (Table 7) by collecting mycelium after 36–48 h and spores are harvested after 72–120 h as per the growth requirement of particular organism in their favorable environment.

Spore germination :

For studying comparative effect of test compound with blank and DMSO agar plate on rate of reproduction, number of germination spores were measured through Haemocytometer (originally devised for counting blood cell).

Morphology :

Observations on the change in morphology of test fungi due to the effect of amide and its complex were examined under Dewinter Digital microscope at 40x after exposure to concentration of 0.76 mg amide/ml media. Comparative studies of morphology on both fungal species with their normal growth and growth within the solvent DMSO were also undertaken.

Biochemical studies :

Effect on the concentration of macromolecule constituents i.e. carbohydrate and nucleic acid viz. DNA and RNA through anthrone, diphenylamine and orcinol method respectively were also studied after growing fungus in presence and absence of terephthalic dihydrazide and its complex and effects were also studied on comparison with concentration of constituents in fungus grown in presence of solvent DMSO also.

Conclusion

This research work is to utilize non-biodegradable PET waste through recycling by aminolysis to get useful end products and to evaluate its potential on multiresistive standard microorganism strains so that they can be used in pharmacological area as such or by emphasizing its biocidal activity through complexation with other well known potential compound. On the basis of the data obtained through elemental and spectral analysis the forma-

tion of amide and its complexes was confirmed and their proposed structures were outlined. Comparative studies between amide and its complex revealed that amide is more effective antifungal agent as compare to its complex. Although degree of susceptibility of test fungi is different, as variable results were produced for size, color and density at different concentration of TDH and its complex. However, the results obtained from studies for MIC shows resistivity at same concentration i.e. 0.8 mg/ml of media. TDH alters the normal morphology of both fungal strains in one and another way. It either caused aberrant development of hyphae, total dispersion and distortion of micro and macroconidia or effects smoothness of wall. It also gave remarkable decrease in the growth region and dry weight measurement of fungi. Studies on the effect of spores and mycelia of test fungi reveal that spores are more susceptible against TDH. Similar results were observed for effect of TDH on reproduction. In study of biochemical changes, carbohydrate concentration decreased in case of both spores and mycelium of *T. lignorum* while increased in case of *F. oxysporum*. In case of nucleic acid content concentration of DNA and RNA has shown inverse results, that their concentration increases in case of both spores and mycelium of *T. lignorum* and decreases in spores and mycelium of *F. oxysporum*.

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